

Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II) Complexes with Nickel(II) Thiocarbohydrazones

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In continuation of our endeavour to synthesise new homo and heterobinuclear complexes with ligands containing N, O and S donor atoms¹⁻⁴, we report here the heterobinuclear complexes of mercury(II) and cadmium(II) with nickel(II) thiocarbohydrazones. The following ligands have been used for preparing the nickel(II) complexes.

I: R = H, II: R = CH₃, III: R = Cl, IV: R = OCH₃

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis (Table 1) suggests the stoichiometry of the binuclear complexes as (NiL)₂MCl₂. The complexes are greenish brown in colour and are soluble in DMF and DMSO. The molar conductance values (in DMF at the concentration of 10⁻³M) are too low to account for any dissociation of the complexes. Hence, these complexes can be regarded as non-electrolytes.

The spectral features of the Ni^{II} complexes with thiocarbohydrazones have been reported earlier³. The ir bands of the Ni^{II} complexes (3 200–1 200 cm⁻¹) are not affected. However, the band due to $\nu_{C=S}$ at 750 cm⁻¹ for nickel(II) thiocarbohydrazones shifts to lower frequency and is observed as a broad band of medium intensity around 700 cm⁻¹ in these binuclear com-

plexes. In addition to the ν_{Ni-N} and ν_{Ni-O} bands, a few new bands are observed at 353–340 and 308–260 cm⁻¹, being attributed to the ν_{M-S} and ν_{M-O} vibrations in view of the previous assignments⁵.

The parent nickel(II) complexes are diamagnetic and hence they are square-planar.

The magnetic moments observed for binuclear complexes fall in the range 3.53–4.00 B.M. indicating that nickel(II) has undergone a configurational change. It is reported that the magnetic moment of truly tetrahedral nickel(II) is 4.2 B.M. at room temperature and distortion in tetrahedral configuration reduces the magnetic moments⁶. Thus it may be concluded that in these binuclear complexes nickel(II) may have distorted tetrahedral configuration. The spectra of nickel(II) thiocarbohydrazone complexes in DMF compare well with the spectra of the same complexes in nujol, indicating that there is no impact of donor solvent on the spectral features of nickel(II) complexes⁷. However, changes are envisioned in the spectra of these complexes over a period of 4–5 h. These nickel(II) complexes exhibit medium intensity broad bands at 14 710–15 500 and 22 730–21 740 cm⁻¹, attributed to the ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transitions respectively, in view of the previous assignments^{6,7}. Binuclear complexes exhibit two band maxima at 16 120–13 900 cm⁻¹. It is reported that tetrahedral nickel(II) complexes give rise to moderate intensity bands at 16 667–14 286 and 8 000–7 143 cm⁻¹. The observed high intensity band in the region 16 120–13 900 cm⁻¹ reveals that nickel(II) has tetrahedral configuration in these complexes. This band is attributed to the ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$ transition.

The results lead us to conclude that the square-planar nickel(II) complexes of thiocarbohydrazones have

TABLE I – ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
	Ni	Cd/Hg	N	S
(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ SNi) ₂ .CdCl ₂	12.74 (12.70)	12.17 12.19	12.10 12.11	6.93 6.91
(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ SNi) ₂ .CdCl ₂	12.30 (12.32)	11.83 11.50	11.73 11.41	6.70 6.52
(C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ SCl ₂ Ni) ₂ .CdCl ₂	11.00 (11.06)	10.61 10.61	10.51 10.54	6.00 6.02
(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ SNi) ₂ .CdCl ₂	11.27 (11.25)	10.72 10.76	10.72 10.73	6.01 6.13
(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ SNi) ₂ .HgCl ₂	11.63 (11.61)	19.80 19.79	11.00 11.06	6.35 6.32
(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ SNi) ₂ .HgCl ₂	11.30 (11.29)	19.30 18.75	10.71 10.47	6.05 5.98
(C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ SCl ₂ Ni) ₂ .HgCl ₂	10.25 (10.21)	17.46 17.44	9.76 9.74	5.59 5.56
(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ SNi) ₂ .HgCl ₂	10.41 (10.37)	17.69 17.70	9.91 9.92	5.62 5.65

been transformed into tetrahedral configuration as a result of reaction with HgCl₂/CdCl₂.

Experimental

Substituted salicylaldehydes, thiocarbohydrazide² and thiocarbohydrazones³ were prepared by known methods.

Nickel(II) thiocarbohydrazone complexes were prepared according to the reported method²⁻⁴. The complexes were purified by extracting them with alcohol. The elemental analyses of these complexes indicate the formation of 1 : 1 complexes of the type ML.

Cd^{II}/Hg^{II} binuclear complexes : A mixture of nickel(II) thiocarbohydrazone (0.02 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) and cadmium(II)/mercury(II) chloride (0.012 mol) in ethanol (50 ml), was refluxed for 3 h. The separated

complex was filtered washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over fused calcium chloride.

The metal contents of the complexes were determined gravimetrically⁸. Nitrogen was determined by Dumas method, sulphur gravimetrically as BaSO₄ and chloride gravimetrically as AgCl.

Conductance measurements were made with an ELICO CM-82 conductivity bridge using a cell of cell constant 0.982. The magnetic susceptibility at room temperature was determined on a Gouy balance using HgCo(SCN)₄ as a calibrant. Electronic spectra (DMF) were recorded on a Hitachi 200-20 spectrophotometer and infrared spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

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